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Conflict Management Between Teaching And Non-Teaching Staff As A Tool For Enhancing Effective Administration In Public Universities In Rivers State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The study explored conflict management between teaching and non-teaching staff as a tool for enhancing effective administration in public universities in Rivers State, Nigeria. It was guided by three objectives, with corresponding research questions and hypotheses. A descriptive survey design was adopted, targeting a population of 6,963 staff across the three public universities in the state. From this, a sample of 696 participants (10%) was selected using a stratified random sampling technique to ensure fair representation. Data were collected using a researcher-developed, validated questionnaire titled: Management of Teaching and Non-Teaching Staff Conflicts for Effective Administration in Public Universities Questionnaire (MTNTSCEAPUQ). The instrument contained 21 items rated on a modified 4-point Likert scale: Strongly Agree, Agree, Disagree, and Strongly Disagree. It achieved a reliability coefficient of 0.82, established through Cronbach's Alpha. Descriptive statistics (mean and standard deviation) were used to analyze the research questions, while the z-test was employed to test the hypotheses at a 0.05 significance level. Findings revealed that effective conflict management significantly contributes to improved university administration. Specifically, addressing challenges such as unequal attention to staff welfare, uneven resource allocation, and inferiority complex among non-teaching staff promotes institutional harmony and cooperation. The study concluded that fair and inclusive conflict resolution strategies are essential for sustainable administration. It was recommended among others, that the government should ensure equitable treatment of all university staff unions, including equal access to welfare provisions, as a way to prevent conflict and enhance overall administrative effectiveness in public universities.

Keywords: Management, Teaching Staff, Non-Teaching Staff, Effective Administration

INTRODUCTION

Universities, as citadels of knowledge, play a crucial role in national development by fostering education, research, and innovation. The smooth functioning of universities depends significantly on the synergy between two main categories of personnel: teaching (academic) and non-teaching (administrative and

support) staff. However, in many public universities in Nigeria, this synergy is frequently undermined by persistent conflicts between these two groups. Such conflicts, if unmanaged, adversely affect institutional efficiency, staff morale, and ultimately the quality of educational services delivered. Therefore, understanding and managing conflicts between teaching and non-teaching staff is central to achieving effective university administration.

A significant source of friction stems from the unequal attention to staff welfare. In most Nigerian public universities, academic staff tend to receive more benefits, recognition, and opportunities for advancement compared to their non-teaching counterparts. For instance, academic staff are often prioritized in training programs, conference sponsorships, and housing schemes (Ogunyemi, 2021). In contrast, non-teaching staff, who are integral to the institution's administrative and operational backbone, frequently feel neglected in welfare considerations. This imbalance fuels dissatisfaction, resentment, and industrial actions, often orchestrated by non-teaching staff unions such as the Senior Staff Association of Nigerian Universities (SSANU) and Non-Academic Staff Union (NASU), all of which disrupt administrative harmony and service delivery (Akomolafe & Ibijola, 2020).

Another driver of conflict is the uneven allocation of institutional resources, particularly in budgeting, infrastructure development, and professional opportunities. Academic departments often receive a greater share of institutional resources under the justification of research and teaching needs, while administrative departments, despite their centrality to record keeping, admissions, finance, and student services, are left underfunded. This perceived favoritism in resource distribution exacerbates inter-staff tensions and creates a sense of marginalization among non-academic staff (Edeh & Ogbonnaya, 2022). For instance, while faculty offices may be equipped with modern technologies and facilities, many registry and bursary units operate with outdated equipment and limited staff training opportunities, further widening the professional gap between both groups.

Additionally, the inferiority complex experienced by non-teaching staff contributes to intergroup tensions. This psychological and organizational phenomenon arises from the structural and cultural elevation of teaching staff in the university hierarchy. Academics often hold decision-making powers in the senate and governing councils, reinforcing a sense of elitism that can marginalize non-academic personnel. This systemic undervaluation of non-teaching roles breeds feelings of low self-worth, defensiveness, and passive resistance among affected staff, all of which can escalate into open conflicts (Oyesola & Lawal, 2020). In some cases, non-teaching staff adopt obstructionist behaviors, delay processes, or refuse cooperation with academics, leading to breakdowns in communication and workflow disruptions.

These conflict triggers welfare disparity, resource misallocation, and status-based insecurity, have compounded over time, leading to recurring industrial disputes, strikes, and strained work relationships in Nigerian public universities. Such tensions compromise not only the internal atmosphere but also the institutions' reputation, student experiences, and broader educational goals. According to the National Universities Commission (NUC, 2023), several public universities have suffered declines in academic productivity, administrative effectiveness, and stakeholder confidence due to unresolved staff conflicts.

Conflict in itself is not inherently detrimental; it can be constructive when managed effectively. However, in many Nigerian universities, conflict resolution mechanisms are either weak, reactive, or biased. Most institutions lack functional conflict management frameworks that promote dialogue, inclusiveness, and mutual respect. Conflict is often addressed after escalation rather than being prevented through proactive and equitable organizational practices (Afolabi, 2021). The failure to institutionalize robust conflict management structures has perpetuated a cycle of antagonism, mutual suspicion, and low morale across staff categories.

The conflict between teaching and non-teaching staff in Nigerian public universities stems from a combination of structural inequality, administrative biases, and cultural perceptions of status. Addressing these root causes through effective conflict management is essential for institutional stability and performance. A sustainable solution must go beyond temporary fixes and embrace a holistic approach that values all staff as stakeholders in university development. Only then can public universities achieve the

administrative effectiveness necessary for fulfilling their mission in national development (Adeyemi & Ogundele, 2019). Therefore, this study sought to examine conflict management between teaching and non-teaching staff as a tool for enhancing effective administration in public universities in Rivers State, Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

The effective administration of public universities in Nigeria is increasingly threatened by persistent and often poorly managed conflicts between teaching and non-teaching staff. While both groups play indispensable roles in the functioning of the university system, tensions between them have escalated due to perceived and actual inequalities in welfare, resource allocation, and organizational status. A key issue lies in the unequal attention to staff welfare, where academic staff are often given preferential treatment in terms of remuneration, training opportunities, and career advancement, while non-teaching staff face neglect and stagnation in their professional development. This disparity not only breeds dissatisfaction but also weakens institutional harmony.

In addition, the uneven allocation of resources has further widened the rift between these two staff categories. Academic departments typically receive more funding for facilities, equipment, and operational support, whereas administrative and support units frequently operate under resource constraints. This lopsided distribution creates resentment among non-teaching staff, who feel marginalized despite their critical role in maintaining the administrative and operational backbone of the institution. Compounding these issues is the development of an inferiority complex among non-teaching staff, stemming from a hierarchical university structure that often places teaching staff at the top of decision-making bodies. Non-academic staff are frequently excluded from key administrative processes, leading to a sense of invisibility and reduced morale. This psychological barrier contributes to communication breakdowns, passive resistance, and strained working relationships.

Despite the existence of grievance procedures and staff unions, many universities lack effective conflict management mechanisms that promote equity, inclusiveness, and respect. As a result, recurring disputes disrupt academic calendars, delay administrative processes, and erode trust within the institutional community. If left unaddressed, these conflicts will continue to undermine the efficiency and stability of public universities in Nigeria. Thus, there is a pressing need to investigate and implement sustainable conflict management strategies that bridge the divide between teaching and non-teaching staff, and promote collaborative, inclusive, and effective university administration.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The study aimed to examine conflict management between teaching and non-teaching staff as a tool for enhancing effective administration in public universities in Rivers State, Nigeria. The objectives of the study sought to:

4. find out the ways teaching and non-teaching staff conflicts due to unequal attention to staff welfare are managed for effective administration of universities in Rivers State.
5. ascertain the ways teaching and non-teaching staff conflicts due to uneven allocation of resources are managed for effective administration of universities in Rivers State.
6. identify the ways teaching and non-teaching staff conflicts due to inferiority complex on the part of the non-teaching staff are managed for effective administration of universities in Rivers State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What are the ways for managing teaching and non-teaching staff conflicts due to unequal attention to staff welfare for effective administration of Universities in Rivers State?
2. What are the ways for managing teaching and non-teaching staff conflicts emanating from uneven allocation of resources for effective administration of Universities in Rivers State?
3. What are the ways teaching and non-teaching staff conflicts due to inferiority complex on the part of non-teaching staff managed for effective administration of Universities in Rivers State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

- Ho₁. There is no significant difference between the mean rating scores of teaching and non-teaching staff on the ways of managing teaching and non-teaching staff conflicts due to unequal attention to staff welfare for effective administration of Universities in Rivers State.
- Ho₂. There is no significant difference between the mean rating scores of teaching and non-teaching staff on the ways teaching and non-teaching staff conflicts emanating from uneven allocation of resources are managed for effective administration of Universities in Rivers State.
- Ho₃. There is no significant difference in the mean rating scores of teaching and non-teaching staff on the ways teaching and non-teaching staff conflicts due to inferiority complex on the part of non-teaching staff are managed for effective administration in Universities in Rivers State.

METHODOLOGY

This research employed a descriptive survey design, deemed appropriate for examining an existing condition to present it in its actual context. The target population consisted of all 6,963 teaching and non-teaching staff across the three public universities in Rivers State: University of Port Harcourt (UNIPORT), Rivers State University (RSU), and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education (IAUE). This data was sourced from the Personnel Affairs Unit of UNIPORT (2024), the Establishment Division of RSU, and the Staff Payroll records of IAUE (2024). A sample size of 696 respondents, representing 10% of the entire population, was selected for the study. The sample included 348 teaching staff and 348 non-teaching staff, chosen through the proportionate stratified random sampling method. This ensured equal representation and fair selection from both categories within each institution. The population was initially stratified into teaching and non-teaching groups for each of the three universities, after which 10% from each subgroup was randomly selected from all faculties using the proportionate technique.

The instrument used for data collection was a researcher-developed questionnaire titled Management of Teaching and Non-Teaching Staff Conflicts for Effective Administration in Public Universities Scale (MTNTSCEAPUS). This univariate instrument was divided into two sections. Section A captured the demographic details of the respondents, while Section B contained 21 scale items grouped into three sub-sections, each comprising 7 items. The sub-sections focused on: communication gaps, competition over earned allowances, and disparities in salary scales. The items were rated using a modified 4-point Likert scale: Strongly Agree (4 points), Agree (3 points), Disagree (2 points), and Strongly Disagree (1 point). Respondents were instructed to select the option that best reflected their views.

To ensure the instrument's quality, validity and reliability tests were conducted. The Cronbach Alpha method was used to determine internal consistency, appropriate for a one-time, dichotomously scored administration. The reliability coefficients for the subscales were as follows: 0.79 for Communication Gap, 0.81 for Competition for Earned Allowances, and 0.82 for Disparity in Salary Scale, with an overall reliability coefficient of 0.82, indicating that the instrument was dependable for the study. Out of the 696 questionnaires distributed, 661 were returned and deemed suitable for analysis, giving a retrieval rate of about 95%. Data were analyzed using Mean and Standard Deviation to address the research questions, while z-test statistics were used to test the three null hypotheses at the 0.05 significance level. A criterion mean of 2.50 was adopted to determine agreement levels—items scoring below 2.50 were considered as "Disagree," whereas scores of 2.50 and above were interpreted as "Agree."

RESULTS AND DATA ANALYSIS

Research Question One: *What are the ways teaching and non-teaching staff conflicts due to unequal attention to staff welfare are managed for effective administration of Universities in Rivers State?*

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation Ratings on the Ways Teaching and Non-Teaching Staff Conflicts due to Unequal Attention to Staff Welfare are Managed for Effective Administration of Universities in Rivers State

S/N	Items	Teaching Staff N = 322		Non-Teaching Staff N = 339		Mean Set	Decision
		\bar{x}_1	SD	\bar{x}_2	SD		
1	Equal provision of welfare payments to both teaching and non-teaching staff to reduce the occurrence of strikes for effective school administration.	3.29	1.24	3.17	1.13	3.23	Agree
2	Fair treatment of all unions in the university should be given more attention by the government and university management as it is important for effectiveness.	3.31	1.11	3.19	1.17	3.25	Agree
3	Fully implementing welfare policies on training of teaching and non-teaching staff by the government and university management creates chances for effective administration.	3.00	1.02	3.02	1.04	3.01	Agree
4	The conduct of promotions at the appropriate time by university management for deserving non-teaching staff just as it is for teaching staff could improve university administration.	2.99	0.91	2.92	0.92	2.96	Agree
5	An increase in funding for the public universities by the government enables the universities' administrators to provide the necessary infrastructural facilities needed by both teaching and non-teaching staff for effective administration of the institutions.	3.11	1.16	2.90	0.88	3.01	Agree
6	An increase in the benefits of university administrators can improve their effectiveness in school administration.	1.70	0.22	1.63	0.39	1.67	Disagree
7	Effective administration is guaranteed when the leadership of the non-teaching staff in public universities comes together to work in harmony with the leadership of the teaching staff.	3.16	1.19	3.13	1.16	3.15	Agree
Average Mean/Standard Deviation		2.94	0.98	2.85	0.96	2.90	Agree

Data in Table 1 show that item 1, 2, 3, 4, 5 and 7, had weighted mean rating scores above the criterion mean of 2.50 and were agreed on as the ways teaching and non-teaching staff conflicts due to unequal attention to staff welfare are managed for effective administration of Universities in Rivers State. Differently, item 6 had mean rating score below the criterion mean of 2.50 and indicates that respondents

disagree that it is a way teaching and non-teaching staff conflicts due to unequal attention to staff welfare are managed for effective administration of Universities in Rivers State.

In summary, with an aggregate weighted mean of 2.90 above the criterion mean of 2.50, the respondents agree that, the ways teaching and non-teaching staff conflicts due to unequal attention to staff welfare are managed for effective administration of Universities in Rivers State include: equal provision of welfare payments to both teaching and non-teaching staff to reduce the occurrence of strikes for effective school administration, fair treatment of all unions in the university should be given more attention by the government and university management as it is important for effectiveness, fully implementing welfare policies on training of teaching and non-teaching staff by government and university management, appraisal for promotions at the appropriate time by university management for deserving non-teaching staff just as it is for teaching staff, increase in funding of the public universities by the government to enable the universities' administrators to provide necessary infrastructural facilities needed by both teaching and non-teaching staff, and coming together of leadership of the non-teaching staff in public universities together to work in harmony with the leadership of teaching staff.

Research Question Two: *What are the ways for managing teaching and non-teaching staff conflicts emanating from uneven allocation of resources for effective administration of Universities in Rivers State?*

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation Ratings on the Ways Teaching and Non-Teaching Staff Conflicts Emanating from Uneven Allocation of Resources can be Managed for Effective Administration of Universities in Rivers State

S/No	Items	Teaching Staff N = 322		Non-Teaching Staff N = 339		Mean Set $\bar{x}_1\bar{x}_2$	Decision
		\bar{x}_1	SD	\bar{x}_2	SD		
8	Setting up a resource allocation committee that comprises the two major unions in the university system is good for administrative efficiency.	2.91	0.97	3.14	1.06	3.03	Agree
9	Contracting the maintenance of university facilities to private organizations to ensure that facilities are properly maintained for even distribution to the two groups guarantees effective administration.	3.95	1.77	2.87	0.91	3.41	Agree
10	Adequate provision of more infrastructural facilities in all public universities in the country is required for effectiveness.	3.65	1.11	3.11	1.08	3.38	Agree
11	Provision of adequate security in all universities in the state to address the problem of vandalisation of available resources is a sign of effectiveness.	3.84	1.50	3.22	1.16	3.53	Agree
12	The deployment of appropriate personnel by the university management to fight all forms of corruption in the allocation of resources in the universities in the state can breed effective administration.	2.97	0.96	3.32	1.22	3.15	Agree
13	Appointment of qualified staff to head the various resource allocation committees in the universities in the state is needed for effective administration.	2.97	0.97	3.32	1.23	3.15	Agree
14	Increment in salaries of both teaching and non-teaching staff of universities enables them to get some facilities for themselves without totally relying on the government.	3.20	1.14	3.21	1.16	3.21	Agree
Grand Mean and Standard Deviation		3.36	1.20	3.17	1.12	3.27	Agree

Data in Table 2 show that all the items (8-14) had mean rating scores above the criterion mean of 2.50 and were adjudged as the ways teaching and non-teaching staff conflicts emanating from uneven allocation of resources are managed for effective administration of Universities in Rivers State.

In summary, with an aggregate weighted mean of 3.27, above the criterion mean of 2.50, the respondents agreed that, the ways teaching and non-teaching staff conflicts emanating from uneven allocation of resources are managed for effective administration of Universities in Rivers State include: setting up resource allocation committee that comprise the two major unions in the university system, contracting the maintenance of university facilities to private organizations to ensure that facilities are properly maintained for even distribution to the two groups, adequate provision of more infrastructural facilities in all public universities in the country, provision of adequate security in all universities in the state to address the problem of vandalisation of available resources, the deployment of appropriate personnel by the university management to fight all forms of corruption in the allocation of resources in the universities in the state, appointment of qualified staff to head the various resource allocation committees in the universities in the state, and increment in salaries of both teaching and non-teaching staff of universities to enable them get some facilities for themselves without totally relying on the government.

Research Question Three: *In what ways are teaching and non-teaching staff conflicts resulting from inferiority complex managed for effective administration of universities in Rivers State?*

Table 3: Mean and Standard Deviation Ratings on the Ways Teaching and Non-Teaching Staff Conflicts Resulting from Inferiority Complex are Managed for Effective Administration of Universities in Rivers State

S/N	Items	Teaching Staff N = 322		Non-Teaching Staff N = 339		Mean Set $\bar{x}_1\bar{x}_2$	Decision
		\bar{x}_1	SD	\bar{x}_2	SD		
15	Non-teaching Staff taking necessary steps to overcome an inferiority complex will lead to effective administration.	3.29	1.20	3.17	1.13	3.23	Agree
16	Non-teaching Staff figuring out who they feel inferior to in the university system will breed effective administration.	3.31	1.33	3.19	1.12	3.25	Agree
17	Non-teaching staff understanding that everyone, including the teaching staff have their own inadequacies is an indicator of effectiveness.	3.00	1.04	3.02	1.04	3.01	Agree
18	Non-teaching staff not wanting to act like teaching staff in the university will enhance effective administration.	2.99	0.97	2.92	0.96	2.96	Agree
19	Non-teaching staff not worrying about what the teaching staff may think about them will lead to effective administration.	3.11	1.06	2.90	0.88	3.01	Agree
20	Building of self-confidence by the non-teaching staff can increase their self-worth for effective work participation.	3.16	1.12	3.13	1.06	3.15	Agree
21	Non-teaching staff not comparing themselves to teaching staff in the university is required for effective administration.	3.29	1.18	3.17	1.13	3.23	Agree
Grand Mean and Standard Deviation		3.16	1.13	3.07	1.05	3.12	Agree

Data in Table 3 show that all the items (15-21) had mean rating scores above the criterion mean of 2.50 and were adjudged as the ways teaching and non-teaching staff conflicts resulting from inferiority complex are managed for effective administration of universities in Rivers State.

In summary, with an aggregate weighted mean of 3.12, above the criterion mean of 2.50, the respondents agree that, the ways teaching and non-teaching staff conflicts resulting from inferiority complex are managed for effective administration of universities in Rivers State include: non-teaching staff taking necessary steps to overcome inferiority complex, non-teaching staff figuring out who they feel inferior to in the university system, non-teaching staff understanding that everyone including the teaching staff have their own inadequacies, non-teaching staff not wanting to act like teaching staff in the university, non-teaching staff not worrying about what the teaching staff may think about them, building of self-confidence by the non-teaching staff to increase their self-worth, and non-teaching staff not comparing themselves to teaching staff in the university.

Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis One (Ho₁): There is no significant difference between the mean rating scores of teaching and non-teaching staff on the ways teaching and non-teaching staff conflicts due to unequal attention to staff welfare are managed for effective administration of Universities in Rivers State.

Table 4: Summary of z-test Analysis of the Difference between the Mean Rating Scores of Teaching and Non-Teaching Staff on the Ways Teaching and Non-Teaching Staff Conflicts due to Unequal Attention to Staff Welfare are Managed for Effective Administration of Universities in Rivers State.

Variable	n	\bar{x}	SD	Df	z-cal.	z-crit.	Level of Significance	Decision
Teaching Staff	322	2.94	0.98	659	1.19	1.96	0.05	Ho ₁ Accepted (Not Significant)
Non-Teaching Staff	339	2.85	0.96					

Legend

n= number of respondents

\bar{x} = mean

SD = Standard deviation

df = degree of freedom

z-cal = z- calculated value

z-crit = z- critical value

The value of z-cal. of 1.19 on Table 4 was less than the value of z-crit. of 1.96, and for this reason, the null hypothesis (Ho₁) was accepted, implying that, there is no significant difference between the mean rating scores of teaching and non-teaching staff on the ways teaching and non-teaching staff conflicts due to unequal attention to staff welfare are managed for effective administration of Universities in Rivers State.

Hypothesis Two (Ho₂): There is no significant difference between the mean rating scores of teaching and non-teaching staff on the ways teaching and non-teaching staff conflicts emanating from uneven allocation of resources are managed for effective administration of Universities in Rivers State.

Table 5: Summary of z-test Analysis of the Difference between the Mean Rating Scores of Teaching and Non-Teaching Staff on the Ways Teaching and Non-Teaching Staff Conflicts Emanating from Uneven Allocation of Resources are Managed for Effective Administration of Universities in Rivers State.

Variable	n	\bar{x}	SD	df	z-cal.	z-crit.	Level of Significance	Decision
Teaching Staff	322	3.36	1.20	659	2.10	1.96	0.05	Ho ₂ Rejected (Significant)
Non-Teaching Staff	339	3.17	1.12					

*The legend for Table 4 applies.

Data in Table 5 indicate that the value of z-cal. of 2.10 was greater than the value of z-crit. of 1.96 at 659 degrees of freedom and 0.05 level of significance and as such, the null hypothesis (Ho₂) was rejected indicating that, there is significant difference between the mean rating scores of teaching and non-teaching staff on the ways teaching and non-teaching staff conflicts emanating from uneven allocation of resources are managed for effective administration of Universities in Rivers State.

Hypothesis Three (Ho₃): There is no significant difference in the mean rating scores of teaching and non-teaching staff on the ways teaching and non-teaching staff conflicts due to inferiority complex on the part of non-teaching staff are managed for effective administration in Universities in Rivers State.

Table 6: Summary of z-test Analysis of the Difference between the Mean Rating Scores of Teaching and Non-Teaching Staff on the Ways Teaching and Non-Teaching Staff Conflicts due to Inferiority Complex on the Part of Non-Teaching Staff are Managed for Effective Administration of Universities in Rivers State.

Variable	n	\bar{x}	SD	Df	z-cal.	z-crit.	Level of Significance	Decision
Teaching Staff	322	3.16	1.13	659	1.05	1.96	0.05	Ho ₇ Accepted (Not Significant)
Non-Teaching Staff	339	3.07	1.05					

*The legend for Table 4 applies.

Data in Table 6 indicate that the value of z-cal. of 1.05 was less than the value of z-crit. of 1.96 at 659 degrees of freedom and 0.05 level of significance and as such, the null hypothesis (H_{03}) was accepted, indicating that, there is no significant difference in the mean rating scores of teaching and non-teaching staff on the ways teaching and non-teaching staff conflicts due to inferiority complex on the part of non-teaching staff are managed for effective administration in Universities in Rivers State.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The first finding of the study revealed that the ways teaching and non-teaching staff conflicts due to unequal attention to staff welfare are managed for effective administration of Universities in Rivers State include: equal provision of welfare payments to both teaching and non-teaching staff to reduce the occurrence of strikes for effective school administration, fair treatment of all unions in the university should be given more attention by the government and university management as it is important for effectiveness, fully implementing welfare policies on training of teaching and non-teaching staff by government and university management, carrying out promotions at the appropriate time by university management for deserving non-teaching staff just as it is for teaching staff, increase in funding of the public universities by the government to enable the universities' administrators to provide necessary infrastructural facilities needed by both teaching and non-teaching staff, and coming together of leadership of the non-teaching staff in public universities together to work in harmony with the leadership of teaching staff.

These findings are in consonance with Abdullahi and Babagana (2019), Kelekun and Adewole, (2020), Ogunode, et al (2021), Agbakwuru and Iyawe (2023) and Madukoma and Opeke (2023) whose comments and empirical research finding present information on the ways for managing teaching and non-teaching staff conflicts due to unequal attention to staff welfare. Explanation for the support in the findings may be in the fact that the respondents themselves were those affected by the unfair treatment of poor staff welfare management, and therefore in a better position to make response, appropriately. These findings imply that management of teaching and non-teaching staff conflicts due to unequal attention to staff welfare will promote effective university administration. Souza (2019) argued that the fair and equal provision of welfare payments to both teaching and non-teaching staff might reduce the occurrence of strikes and malingering, hence enhancing effectiveness and efficiency in the university administration. In view of this, Kelekun and Adewole, (2020) opined that staff in all university institutions should be motivated through a welfare package so as to continue to perform their statutory duties. They maintained that welfare packages are not expected to promote employees' motivation to attain maximum performance unless they are properly implemented. Inequality in the staff welfare package provided would not assist in improving and comforting staff. This is evident in the test of hypothesis, which establishes no significant difference between the mean ratings of teaching and non-teaching staff on the ways teaching and non-teaching staff conflicts due to unequal attention to staff welfare are managed for effective administration of Universities in Rivers State.

The second finding of the study revealed that the ways teaching and non-teaching staff conflicts emanating from uneven allocation of resources are managed for effective administration of Universities in Rivers State include: setting up resource allocation committee that comprise the two major unions in the university system, contracting the maintenance of university facilities to private organizations to ensure that facilities are properly maintained for even distribution to the two groups, adequate provision of more infrastructural facilities in all public universities in the country, provision of adequate security in all universities in the state to address the problem of vandalisation of available resources, the deployment of all human resources by the state government to fight all forms of corruption in the allocation of resources in the universities in the state, appointment of qualified staff to head the various resource allocation committees in the universities in the state, and increment in salaries of both teaching and non-teaching staff of universities to enable them get some facilities for themselves without totally relying on the

government. Also, a corresponding finding from the test of hypothesis establishes a significant difference between the mean ratings of teaching and non-teaching staff on the ways teaching and non-teaching staff conflicts emanating from uneven allocation of resources are managed for effective administration of Universities in Rivers State.

These findings are in line with Mahmud and Nguyiman (2019), Akinola (2019), Salisu (2021), Okolo and Gregory (2021), Bernadette and Ukaegbu, (2021) whose contributions and research findings established that the identified variables are the ways for managing teaching and non-teaching staff conflicts emanating from uneven allocation of resources. A possible explanation for this, may be the fact that the respondents as staff of universities have in several platforms advocated for the identified ways in this study for managing conflicts emanating from uneven allocation of resources in their schools. These findings therefore imply that schools with proper allocation of resources are good in their administration. Concurring further, Salisu (2021) in her study of influence of unequal allocation of physical resources on university staff performance concludes that, there is significant difference in the university staff performance in institutions with adequate and equitable facilities allocation, than those with inadequate and uneven facilities allocation. This situation calls for increased and equitable allocation of resources to various groups in the university, from both the government, educational stakeholders and university management so as to sustain the tempo and growth of education industry for effective administration.

Lastly, the third finding of the study revealed that the ways teaching and non-teaching staff conflicts resulting from inferiority complex are managed for effective administration of universities in Rivers State include: non-teaching staff taking necessary steps to overcome inferiority complex, non-teaching staff figuring out who they feel inferior to in the university system, non-teaching staff understanding that everyone including the teaching staff have their own inadequacies, non-teaching staff not wanting to act like teaching staff in the university, non-teaching staff not worrying about what the teaching staff may think about them, building of self-confidence by the non-teaching staff to increase their self-worth, and non-teaching staff not comparing themselves to teaching staff in the university. These findings are in consonance with Kabir (2018), Bakera (2019), Kazuki (2021), Jing (2022), Gilbert, et al. (2023) who found out in their studies that teaching and non-teaching staff conflicts resulting from inferiority complex are managed in the ways identified. These findings imply that schools without an effective administrative system are those that are not able to manage teaching and non-teaching staff conflicts resulting from an inferiority complex. No wonder the hypothesis tested establishes no significant difference between the mean ratings of teaching and non-teaching staff on the ways teaching and non-teaching staff conflicts due to inferiority complex on the part of non-teaching staff are managed for effective administration in Universities in Rivers State.

CONCLUSION

In view of the findings of the study, it was concluded that effective conflict management between teaching and non-teaching staff is essential for improving university administration in Rivers State. Addressing issues such as unequal staff welfare, imbalanced resource allocation, and the inferiority complex among non-teaching staff can foster mutual respect and institutional harmony.

RECOMMENDATIONS

In light of the findings and conclusions of the study, the following were recommended:

1. The government should give equal attention to all unions and treat them fairly, such as making equal provision of welfare packages to both unions to reduce the occurrence of strikes for effective university administration.
2. The government, in collaboration with university management, should deploy human resources to fight all forms of corruption in the allocation of resources in the universities. This can be

effectively carried out by setting up a resource allocation committee that comprises the two major unions in the university system.

3. The university management should take necessary steps to help the non-teaching staff build their self-worth to overcome an inferiority complex, in order to minimize the level at which they compare themselves to teaching staff in the university.

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